

Short-Term Outcome of Acute Ischemic Stroke Presented After 24 Hours of Onset in Sylhet M.A.G. Osmani Medical College Hospital

Dr. Istahad Abu Zafor Chowdhury ✉

Assistant Professor - Dept. of Medicine, Sylhet M.A.G. Osmani Medical College Hospital, Bangladesh

Prof. Dr. Mohammad Zabed Jilul Bari

Professor and Head Department of Medicine and Principal, Habiganj Medical College, Bangladesh

Dr. Nahia Zafrin

Associate Professor - Department of Medicine, Sylhet M.A.G. Osmani Medical College Hospital, Bangladesh

Dr. Nazrul Islam

Assistant professor - Department of Medicine, Sylhet M.A.G. Osmani Medical College Hospital, Bangladesh

Dr. Ardhendu Shekhor Roy

Junior Consultant- Department of Medicine, Sylhet M.A.G. Osmani Medical College Hospital, Bangladesh

Dr. Nowshin Islam Chowdhury

DA Anesthesia in course, Sylhet M.A.G. Osmani Medical College Hospital, Bangladesh

Dr. Fatema Jannat, MBBS

Diabetic Association Medical College & Hospital, Faridpur, Bangladesh

Abstract

Background: Acute ischemic stroke (AIS) is a major cause of mortality and long-term disability worldwide. Early initiation of treatment plays a decisive role in determining patient outcomes. However, in many developing regions, a large proportion of patients present to hospitals beyond the recommended therapeutic window. This study aimed to evaluate and compare short-term outcomes of AIS patients presenting after 24 hours of symptom onset with those admitted within 24 hours.

Methods: This prospective analytical cross-sectional study was conducted at Sylhet M.A.G. Osmani Medical College Hospital. A total of 120 patients with confirmed acute ischemic stroke were enrolled. Patients presenting more than 24 hours after symptom onset were categorized as cases (n=60), while those presenting within 24 hours were considered controls (n=60). Demographic data, vascular risk factors, stroke severity, functional outcomes at day 7 using the modified Rankin Scale (mRS), and in-hospital mortality were analyzed. Statistical significance was set at $p \leq 0.05$.

Results: Baseline demographic and clinical characteristics were comparable between the two groups. Favorable functional outcomes (mRS ≤ 2) were observed in 13.3% of late presenters compared to 33.3% of early presenters, showing a statistically significant difference. Mortality was higher among patients presenting after 24 hours (26.7%) compared to those presenting earlier (11.7%). Multivariate analysis identified delayed presentation and age ≥ 60 years as independent predictors of poor prognosis.

Conclusion: Delayed hospital presentation following acute ischemic stroke is associated with worse short-term functional outcomes and higher mortality. Improving public awareness, early recognition of stroke symptoms, and strengthening referral systems may help improve outcomes.

More Information

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Introduction

Stroke, also referred to as a cerebrovascular insult, represents an acute disturbance in cerebral blood circulation resulting in impairment of central nervous system function and focal neurological deficits. The World Health Organization (WHO) characterizes stroke as the sudden onset of clinical signs indicating focal or global cerebral dysfunction, persisting for more than 24 hours or resulting in death, with a vascular cause and no other identifiable origin [1]. Stroke is currently the second leading cause of mortality worldwide and ranks third as a cause of long-term disability among adults [2]. The estimated annual incidence of stroke in the general population is approximately 2 per 1,000 individuals [3]. Globally, data from 2013 indicate that nearly 25.7 million people were living with the consequences of stroke, of whom approximately 71% had ischemic stroke. During the same period, stroke accounted for about 6.5 million deaths, with ischemic stroke responsible for more than half of these fatalities. In addition, stroke contributed to nearly 113 million disability-adjusted life years, and an estimated 10.3 million new stroke cases were recorded, the majority being ischemic in nature [4]. In Bangladesh, WHO statistics published in 2014 identified stroke as the fifth leading cause of death [5]. The national prevalence of stroke is estimated at 300 per 100,000 population, reflecting a substantial public health burden [6]. The high number of disability-adjusted life years lost due to stroke highlights its significant economic and social impact in the country [7].

Ischemic stroke is the most common subtype of stroke and occurs when cerebral blood flow is interrupted due to arterial occlusion, most often caused by thrombosis, embolism, or atherosclerotic disease. Reduced delivery of oxygen and nutrients to brain tissue leads to focal or generalized neurological dysfunction and irreversible neuronal injury. Ischemic stroke accounts for approximately 87% of all stroke cases [8]. Clinical manifestations include focal neurological deficits such as cognitive impairment, motor weakness, hemiplegia, sensory loss, impaired coordination, and cranial nerve involvement. Patients may also present with global symptoms, including altered vital signs, abnormal blood pressure, and changes in consciousness such as syncope, seizures, or coma [9,10].

The principle of “time is brain” underscores the critical importance of early intervention in acute ischemic stroke, as prompt treatment significantly improves clinical outcomes [11]. Intravenous recombinant tissue plasminogen activator (rtPA) remains the approved reperfusion therapy for eligible patients with acute ischemic stroke [12], with current guidelines recommending administration within three hours of symptom onset [13]. Evidence suggests that prolonged

cerebral ischemia beyond six hours results in irreversible neurological damage [14]. In addition to thrombolytic therapy, comprehensive acute stroke management—including airway and cardiovascular support, fluid and metabolic regulation, blood pressure control, glycemic and temperature management, and prevention of stroke-related complications—is essential during the early phase of care to improve prognosis [15].

In practice, a substantial proportion of patients with ischemic stroke fail to reach healthcare facilities within the optimal time window. In many resource-limited settings, including ours, rtPA is not readily available, and management is largely limited to supportive measures. Delayed initiation of appropriate care and the inability to administer reperfusion therapy adversely influence patient outcomes. Stroke prognosis is highly variable, ranging from complete recovery to death or long-term disability. Common complications include respiratory infections, deep vein thrombosis, pulmonary embolism, pressure ulcers, urinary tract infections, seizures, recurrent stroke, and psychological disorders such as anxiety and depression [15].

The modified Rankin Scale (mRS) is widely used to assess functional outcomes following stroke. It grades disability on a scale from 0, indicating no symptoms, to 6, representing death [16]. For outcome analysis, mRS scores are often dichotomized into good functional outcome (≤ 2) and poor outcome (> 2) [17]. Previous research from India has demonstrated that patients admitted more than 24 hours after stroke onset experienced poorer in-hospital outcomes compared with those presenting earlier, with higher rates of dependency observed among late presenters [18].

Despite the clinical significance of delayed presentation, limited data are available regarding the short-term outcomes of patients with acute ischemic stroke presenting after 24 hours of symptom onset, particularly in Bangladesh. To date, no such study has been conducted at Sylhet M.A.G. Osmani Medical College Hospital. Therefore, this study was undertaken to evaluate the short-term outcomes of acute ischemic stroke patients presenting after 24 hours of onset at this tertiary care center.

Methods

This prospective observational study was held in the department of Medicine and department of neurology, Sylhet M.A.G. Osmani Medical College Hospital, Sylhet. All acute ischemic stroke patients of 60 were enrolled as case and 60 patients (AIS patients admitted before 24 hours) were considered as control.

within 15/10/18 to 14/4/19. Convenient sampling was used to include the patients with acute ischemic stroke of first attack confirmed by CT scan those who comes after 24 hours. On the other hand, patients with

previous history of head injury were excluded from the study.

Operational definitions

Short-term outcome: Short-term outcome was defined as the patient’s clinical and functional status assessed on the seventh day following stroke onset [19].

Time of stroke onset: The time of stroke onset was considered the moment when the patient or an accompanying individual first recognized the appearance of focal neurological symptoms [20].

Arterial hypertension: Hypertension was identified if it was previously recorded in the patient’s medical history or if blood pressure measurements obtained after the acute phase of stroke showed systolic pressure ≥ 140 mmHg and/or diastolic pressure ≥ 90 mmHg on at least two separate occasions.

Ischemic heart disease: Ischemic heart disease was diagnosed based on a documented history of angina pectoris or previous myocardial infarction.

Diabetes mellitus: Diabetes mellitus was diagnosed according to standard criteria, including any of the following:

- Fasting plasma glucose ≥ 126 mg/dL (7.0 mmol/L), or
- Two-hour plasma glucose ≥ 200 mg/dL (11.1 mmol/L) during an oral glucose tolerance test, or
- Glycated hemoglobin (HbA1c) level $\geq 6.5\%$, or

In individuals with classical symptoms of hyperglycemia or hyperglycemic crisis, a random plasma glucose level ≥ 200 mg/dL (11.1 mmol/L) [21].

Data Processing and Analysis

Before data analysis, an analysis plan was made to analyse the data. Then all data were inputted in the statistical software. Following cleaning and editing the data, the spread sheet was prepared for data analysis. Data processing and analysis were done using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 25. Quantitative data were expressed as mean and standard deviation while Qualitative data were expressed as frequency and percentage. In order to determine the association, chi-square test was used. A probability (p) value of ≤ 0.05 was considered as statistically significant.

Result

Table 1 shows that most patients were 61–70 years old, accounting for 40% of cases and 35% of controls. Male patients predominated in both groups (61.7% in cases and 66.67% in controls).

Female patients made up 38.33% of cases and 33.33% of controls.

Muslims were the majority in both groups (90% in cases and 93.33% in controls).

Overall, no significant differences were found between groups ($p > 0.05$), indicating comparable baseline characteristics.

Table 1: Socio-Demographic Characteristics of the Respondents (n=120)

Distribution of the patients according to age (n=120)			
Age	Case* (%)	Control* (%)	P value**
18-30	3.33%	3.33%	0.575
31-40	5%	6.67%	
41-50	20%	10%	
51-60	15%	23.33%	
61-70	40%	35%	
>70	16.67%	21.67%	
Distribution of the patients according to sex (n=120)			
Sex	Case* (%)	Control* (%)	P value**
Male	61.7%	66.67%	0.352
Female	38.33%	33.33%	
Distribution of the patients according to religion (n=120)			
Religion	Case* (%)	Control* (%)	P value**
Muslim	90%	93.33%	0.372
Hindu	10%	6.67%	

Table 2: Risk Factors (Smoking, TIA and IHD) of Ischemic Stroke (N=120)

Risk factors		Case	Control	Total	P value
Smoking	Yes	26 (43.33)	24 (40)	50 (41.67)	0.427
	No	34 (56.67)	36 (60)	70 (58.33)	
Transient ischemic attack	Yes	05 (8.33)	08 (13.33)	13 (10.83)	0.279
	No	55 (91.67)	52 (86.67)	107 (89.17)	
Ischemic heart disease	Yes	05 (8.33)	04 (6.67)	09 (7.50)	0.500
	No	55 (91.67)	56 (93.33)	111 (92.50)	

Table 2 illustrates risk factors (Smoking, TIA and IHD) of ischemic stroke. In case group history of diabetes was present in 30% of patient and history of hypertension was present in 61.67% of patient. In control group history of diabetes was present in 35% of patient and history of hypertension was present in 29.7% of patient. Among the total study group history of diabetes was present in 32.50% patient and previous history of hypertension was present in 60% patient. History of hypertension and diabetes were matched between case and control group ($p=0.348$ and 0.426).

Table 3 resembles Dyslipidemia and atrial fibrillation among the patients. In case group atrial fibrillation was observed in 5% patient and dyslipidemia was observed in 36.67% patient. In control group atrial fibrillation was observed in 8.33% patient and dyslipidemia was observed in 40% patient. Among total study group atrial fibrillation was observed in 6.67% patient and dyslipidemia was observed in 38.33% patient. Atrial fibrillation and dyslipidemia was matched between two groups ($p=0.359$ and 0.426).

Table 3: Dyslipidemia and Atrial Fibrillation among the Patients (N=120)

Variable		Case	Control	Total	P value
Atrial fibrillation	Yes	03 (05)	05 (8.33)	08 (6.67)	0.359
	No	57 (95)	55 (91.67)	112 (93.33)	
Dyslipidemia	Yes	22 (36.67)	24 (40)	46 (38.33)	0.426
	No	38 (63.33)	36 (60)	74 (61.67)	

Table 4: Severity of Stroke at Admission among the Patients (N=120)

Severity of stroke (Modified NIHSS)	Case	Control	Total	P value
Mild (<5)	02 (3.33)	03 (05)	05 (4.17)	0.805
Moderate (6-14)	28 (46.67)	25 (41.67)	53 (44.17)	
Severe (15-31)	30 (50)	32 (53.33)	62 (51.67)	

Table 4 shows severity of stroke at admission among the patients. According to modified National Institutes of Health Stroke Scale in case group 3.33% had mild stroke, 46.67% had moderate stroke and 50% had severe stroke. In control group 5% had mild stroke, 41.67% had moderate stroke and 53.33% had severe stroke. In total study group 4.17% had mild stroke, 44.17% had moderate stroke and 51.67% had severe stroke. Severity of stroke was matched between the groups ($p=0.805$).

statistically significantly better in control group than case group ($p=0.008$). In case group only 13.33% patient had good functional outcome ($MRS \leq 2$). On the contrary, in control group 33.33% patient had good functional outcome ($MRS > 2$). In total study group 23.33% patient had good functional outcome ($MRS > 2$).

Figure 1: Short Term Functional Outcome of the Patients (N=120)

Figure 1 shows short term functional outcome of the patients. Functional outcome of the patients was

Figure 2: During Study Mortality of the Patients (N=120)

Figure 2 illustrates during study mortality of the patients. It is evident that, mortality of the patients was statistically significantly lower in control group than case group ($p=0.031$). In case group mortality rate was 26.67% while in control group mortality rate was only 11.67%. Total mortality rate was 19.17%.

Table 5: Multivariate Regression Analysis of Risk Factors for Poor Prognosis of Stroke (n=120)

Variables	Odds ratio	95% CI	p-value
Age (≥60)	3.625	1.378 – 9.535	0.009
Sex	0.340	0.087-1.328	0.121
Patients came after 24 hours	3.879	1.417 – 10.620	0.008
DM	0.662	0.242 – 1.814	0.423
Hypertension	0.973	0.329 – 2.877	0.961
Hyperlipidemia	0.927	0.342 – 2.512	0.881
Smoking	1.197	0.371 – 3.857	0.764
TIA	1.258	0.228 – 6.953	0.792
IHD	0.271	0.053 – 1.382	0.116

Multivariate regression analysis of various risk factors for poor prognosis of ischemic stroke was conducted. Significant findings include that patients who presented after 24 hours of stroke onset had higher odds of poor prognosis (OR = 3.879, p = 0.008).

Discussion

Stroke is defined by the World Health Organization as the sudden onset of focal or global neurological dysfunction of vascular origin, persisting for more than 24 hours or resulting in death [22]. It remains a leading contributor to mortality, long-term disability, and social dependence worldwide. WHO estimates indicate that approximately 5.7 million deaths and 16 million first-ever stroke events occurred globally in 2005, with projections suggesting these figures may rise to 7.8 million deaths and 23 million new cases by 2030 [23]. The present prospective observational study was conducted to evaluate short-term outcomes among patients with acute ischemic stroke presenting more than 24 hours after symptom onset, in comparison with those presenting within 24 hours.

No statistically significant differences were observed between the case and control groups with regard to mean age or age distribution (p=0.519 and p=0.575). These findings are consistent with a study by Bhowmik and colleagues, who reported a mean age of 60.6 years, with 66% of patients aged over 45 years [24].

Male patients constituted the majority of cases in the present study, accounting for 64.2%, while females represented 35.8%. The gender distribution did not differ significantly between the two groups (p=0.352). Similar male predominance has been reported by Masum et al., who found 64.6% of their study population to be male [25]. Comparable findings were also documented by Khanam et al. and Islam et al., with male proportions of 57.5% and 74%, respectively [7,26].

In terms of religious background, the majority of participants were Muslim (91.7%), with Hindus comprising 8.3% of the study population. These results closely resemble those reported by Masum and associates, who observed a similar distribution in their cohort [27].

Common vascular risk factors—including previous transient ischemic attack, ischemic heart disease, atrial fibrillation, and hyperlipidemia—were evenly distributed between the case and control groups, with no statistically significant differences. These findings align with the observations reported by Alam and colleagues [28].

Assessment of stroke severity using the modified National Institutes of Health Stroke Scale revealed that 4.17% of patients had mild stroke, 44.17% had moderate stroke, and 51.67% had severe stroke at presentation. Stroke severity was comparable between the two groups (p=0.805). Hasan et al. reported a similar pattern, with the majority of patients presenting with moderate to severe stroke [29].

Functional outcome analysis demonstrated that favorable recovery (mRS ≤2) was significantly less frequent among patients presenting after 24 hours (13.33%) compared with those presenting earlier (33.33%). Mortality was also significantly higher in the late-presentation group (26.67%) than in the early-presentation group (11.67%) (p=0.031). Both univariate and multivariate regression analyses identified delayed hospital presentation as a significant predictor of poor prognosis (p<0.05).

These findings are consistent with a study by Mittal and co-researchers, who reported significantly longer delays in hospital presentation among patients who died compared with those who were discharged (47.51 ± 39.73 hours vs. 22.55 ± 43.07 hours; p=0.006) [30]. Similarly, Nayak and colleagues observed higher rates of clinical improvement among patients presenting within 24 hours compared with those presenting later (90% vs. 79%) [18].

Conclusion

Overall, the findings indicate meaningful differences in functional outcome and mortality between the groups despite comparable baseline characteristics. Interpretation should be cautious, as the study was limited by its sample size and single-center design. Future research with larger, multi-center cohorts could help confirm these results and explore additional factors influencing recovery. Strengthening early

assessment and tailored interventions may further enhance patient outcomes.

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